

A Study of Phonetics and Phonological Features of Pakistani English

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to describe the phonetic-phonological features of Pakistani English in relation to the Standard variety of British English. Pakistani English is an institutionalized non-native variety of English that has developed formal feature at all linguistic levels. However, it is best recognized by its phonological characteristics, despite the fact that phonological variation is widespread. The researcher has examined the phonetics and phonological features of Pakistani English in this study, starting with broad, systemic differences before moving on to a comprehensive analysis of specific consonants, vowels, and non-segmental features. The findings suggest that Pakistani English's phonetics and phonological features deviate considerably from those of Received Pronunciation, which is the result of first language interference.

Introduction

Linguistic divergences have given rise to various varieties of English that have emerged in areas where English is commonly used as a second language. In recent years, initial skepticism toward these varieties has given way to a more accepting stance. As a result, numerous new varieties of English are gradually but surely being accepted in various parts of the world, and linguists are investigating their different aspects. Pakistani English is one such variety that has recently made its mark on the linguistic landscape of the world.

The notion that Pakistani English is indeed a unique variety assumes that the English language in Pakistan has undergone a process of "Pakistanization," which manifests itself formally in a manner similar to that of Americanization, Australianization, or Canadianization. This phenomenon of Pakistanization has resulted in distinct Pakistani features in the Pakistani variety of English at all linguistic levels, because of the use of the English language in new sociocultural settings of Pakistan, in contact with other Pakistani languages, and in the absence of native speakers of English. Sidhwa (1993), commenting on the Pakistanization of English in Pakistan, says:

We, the ex-colonized, have just subjugated the language [English], beaten it on its head and made it ours! Let the English chafe and fret and fume. The fact remains that in adapting English to our use, in hammering it sometimes on its head, and in sometimes twisting its tail, we have given it a new shape, substance, and dimension (p. 212).

Since, the Pakistani variety of English is still closely related to British English's core grammar, on which it is based, some dissenters question its validity as a distinct viable variety of English. They believe that certain features peculiar to Pakistani English are not as widespread as others: some are common but not overly so; others are ubiquitous or almost universal; and still others appear to arise in a random, irregular manner. Moreover, those who doubt the existence of Pakistani English as a distinct variation ask, If there is such a variety, what are the distinct features that enable us to recognize it? Are these differences strong enough to classify Pakistani English as a distinct language? Furthermore, they require scientific descriptions of it.

It appears legitimate to ask for a scientific description of Pakistani English. While there is no doubt that Pakistani English exists, defining it in specific linguistic terms and figuring out exactly what Pakistani English entails requires substantial investigation. This would have to account for the changes in the English language at various levels of phonetics-phonology, morpho-syntax, lexico-semantics and pragmatics as a result of its usage in the Pakistani socio-cultural setting, so that the whole diversity of this variation can be revealed.

Since, Pakistani English is best recognized by its phonetics and phonological characteristics, despite the fact that phonological variation is widespread. Although Received Pronunciation (henceforth RP) is the norm, English pronunciation does not follow a consistent pattern across Pakistan. It is because of the influence of diverse ethnolinguistic backgrounds of Pakistani English speakers. Pakistan is a multilingual country with at least 69

living languages; as a result, the phonetics and phonology of the Pakistani variant of English is generally determined by the phonetic and phonological structure of the speaker's mother tongue.

In this backdrop, the researcher sets out to analyze some aspects of phonetics and phonology of Pakistani English in relation to the Standard Variety of British English. However, the task is far from straightforward, because Pakistani English is not uniform from region to region, but varies according to the linguistic and ethnic backgrounds of its speakers. For example, certain features may be unique to one area of Pakistan, while others may be unique to another, reflecting the substratum influence of the Indo-Aryan and Indo-Persian language groups, which must inevitably affect the English usage of most Pakistanis. Apart from that, Pakistani users' English proficiency varies greatly depending on their level of proficiency in the language.

As a result, a cline of proficiency exists for Pakistani English, as is the case with every second language variety, at all linguistic levels, including pronunciation, grammar, and lexis. Therefore, pronunciation variations amongst speakers are pretty common in Pakistani English. Thus, this research work aims to analyze some of the phonetic-phonological aspects of Pakistani English in comparison with the RP. The following are the research questions that comprise the focus of this study.

1. What characteristics of Pakistani English's phonetics and phonology set it apart from RP?
2. Why is the Pakistani English different from RP in terms of phonetics and phonological features?

Although, it is important to note that the phonetics and phonological features of Pakistani English which set it apart from RP are not absolute differences, they are consistent and they can be accounted for by means of systematic rules, which differentiate the Pakistani variety of English at the phonetics and phonological level from the RP.

Literature Review

Since, Pakistani English is a contact induced variety, that developed as a result of contact between the English and indigenous languages in the region that now comprises Pakistan, it is inevitable that it will develop its own distinctive features at all linguistic levels, such as phonetic-phonology, morpho-syntax, lexico-semantics and pragmatics. However, the variations between Pakistani English and other native varieties of English are easiest to perceive on a phonological level. Despite this, little research has been done on the phonetics and phonology of Pakistani English. The following works by Kachru (1994), Rahman (1990; 2014), Mahboob and Ahmar (2004), and Khan (2012) that explore the phonetics and phonological characteristics of Pakistani English are noteworthy.

The review of the phonetics and phonological features of Pakistani English are divided into segmental features and non-segmental features.

Segmental Features

Segmental features of the Pakistani variety of English mainly include consonants and vowels, as well as some other aspects, which are reviewed as under:

- a. Rahman (1990) says that in Pakistani English the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ are replaced by /tʰ/ and /d/. This is also true for Indian speakers of English (Barron, 1961) who also do not have /θ/ and /ð/ in their languages. This is referred to as a case of transfer to substitution of elements from a second language into the first language by Kachru (1969, p.27). However, unless their attention is deliberately directed to it, Pakistani speakers do not discern the phonetic difference between the realization and acoustic quality of these English phonemes and their own substitutes (p. 27).
- b. The consonants /p,t,k/ are not aspirated at the start of a word or at the start of stressed syllables. Because, spirated and unaspirated consonants are independent phonemes in Urdu, Punjabi, and Sindhi, and form minimum pairs (Rahman, 1990, pp. 27-28).
- c. Retroflex stops /ɖ, ɗ/ take the role of alveolar stops /t, d/. This, too, is a swap of second language elements for first language elements. "The entire alveolar series is replaced by a retroflex sequence" (p.28) in South Asian English, as Kachru (1969) correctly points out. Mahboob and Ahmar (2004) agree with Rahman (1990) that retroflex stops are used in Pakistani English. Other English varieties' alveolar stops are represented by [t] and [d]. Kachru (1992, p. 62) lists this usage of retroflex stops instead of RP alveolar stops as an example of 'series substitution' and it is a characteristic of South Asian English. Retroflex stops are used in the following examples: [t] and [d] in Pakistani English are: [ɪsɪɾʌt] 'strut' and [ɖɾes] 'dress.' Moreover, Sindhi and Urdu speakers experience the retroflexion more than others. Most speakers, however, do not notice the phonetic difference between the RP and their own pronunciation of these stops until their attention is drawn to it first (p. 30).
- d. Monophthongs are used to substitute some diphthongs in RP. Thus, in some pairings, /ou/ and /ev/ are substituted by /o:/ and /e:/, respectively, and /ə/ is erased. Trudgill and Hannah (1982, p. 106) list this as one of the characteristics of Indian English, while Barron (1961b) and Bansal (1962) explain it. The diphthongs /ou/ and /ev/ are lacking from Urdu's vowel system, according to Bansal (1962). They are

- likewise absent from Punjabi, Sindhi, and Pashto languages. As a result, even highly educated Pakistani English speakers tend to replace monophthongs in their place.
- e. In Pakistani English, according to Rahman (1990), the /l/ is not velarized in RP positions. It is retroflexed, though, because it is one of the alveolar phonemes. As a result, both the allophones [l] and [ɭ] are represented by /l/. The reason for this is that in Punjabi, Urdu, Pashto, and Sindhi, /l/ has no alternative allophone; hence speakers of these languages only employ one phoneme of /l/ in all locations. Likewise, Mahboob and Ahmar (2004) say that all realisations of /l/ were “clear”. This is also a trait of South Asian English, according to Kachru (1992, p. 62). In RP, a clear [l] and a dark [ɭ] have an allophonic distribution. When it appears in the final place of a word or followed by a consonant, /l/ is realised as ‘dark’ or velarized [ɭ]. In all other circumstances, it is pronounced [l], which is a ‘clear’ or alveolar [l]. The following examples demonstrate that Pakistani speakers lack this allophonic variation: [go:l] ‘goal’ and [lɔ:t] ‘lot’ (p. 253).
 - f. Think is said in Pashto with /t/ instead of /th/. This is because the glottal fricative /h/ (Mackenzie, 1987, p. 550) is sounded as a vowel in Pashto.
 - g. The vowels /ɔ:/ and /ɒ/ in RP are sometimes substituted by /ɑ:/. Bansal (1962) investigated the Hindi vowel system, and his results that these vowels do not exist in Hindi apply to Urdu and other Pakistani languages as well. As a result, horse and cot are pronounced as /ha:rs/ and /ka:t/, respectively. Most speakers of this variety of English, however, utilize a vowel sound that is closer to the back and half-open.
 - h. In Pakistani English, the distinction between /v/ and /w/ is usually not made. This is due to the fact that they are not distinguishable in Hindi, according to Rao (1961), who has examined this aspect in Indian English. Yamuna Kachru (1987, p. 472) lists /w/ as a Hindi-Urdu phoneme, but /v/ as a Persianized Urdu phoneme. Furthermore, Mahboob and Ahmar (2004) claim that there is no phonemic difference between /v/ and /w/ in Urdu. There is no phonemic difference between [v] and [w] in Pakistani English, either. The two sounds were realized as /w/ allophones. The pronunciation of the word wind, for example, was either [vɪnd] or [wɪnd] (p. 253).
 - i. Pakistani English, according to Mahboob and Ahmar (2004), might be classified as a rhotic variety of English. Most speakers pronounce [r] in all instances, including after a vowel. Individual speakers did not always pronounce the postvocalic [r] in the same way. For every individual speaker, however, the presence or absence of [r] was not unequivocal. The same speaker, for example, was seen using [r] in start, cure, and letter but dropping it in force (p. 252). The degree of rhoticity in Pakistani English varies as per sociolinguistic conditions, according to Rahman (1990). He contends that speakers of an acrolectal variation of Pakistani English can either pronounce or not pronounce postvocalic [r] occurrences. However, there is no discussion of the actual prevalence of rhoticity among acrolectal Pakistani English speakers. He goes on to say that the mesolectal and basilectal varieties of Pakistani English are both rhotic, with speakers pronouncing [r] in all situations.
 - j. Pakistani English spelling influences pronunciation, but not fully, in the educated variety. As a result, speakers of this variety of English can use the spelling to help them pronounce unfamiliar words, especially those with non-English pronunciations. Mahboob and Ahmar (2004) agree with Rahman (1990) that spelling is often used as a guide to pronunciation in Pakistani English. The gemination of consonants dependent on spelling is one example of this. For example, in [hæppi] happy and [lettɑr] letter, all of the speakers geminated the [p] and [t]. In related speech, gemination was also seen. For example, all speakers quickly geminated the [m] consonant in [ɪmmɪdʒetli]. However, there were exceptions to germination. Such as, the term wrapped, for example, was a frequent exception (p. 254).

Non-Segmental Features

South Asian English’s originality, according to Kachru (1983), is defined by non-segmental qualities like as stress and rhythm rather than segmental features. While segmental features of South Asian Englishes are greatly impacted by mother languages, he claims that non-segmental features are universal. The stress pattern in South Asian English is one of the most common examples he and other linguists working on the language offer.

The rhythm of the two types is further affected by variations in stress between RP and South Asian English (es) (as well as a lack of vowel reduction in South Asian English). Different research studies indicate that the stress patterns of various sub-varieties of South Asian English are identical and are unaffected by the speakers’ first languages. Pickering and Wiltshire (2000) have examined South Asian English (es) spoken by native speakers of Hindi/Urdu, Bengali, and Tamil and discovered no significant differences in lexical stress patterns across the three languages. This confirms Kachru’s (1983) claim that South Asian English (es) share non-segmental features.

Such as, English is stress-timed, but most South Asian languages are syllable-timed (Nelson, 1982). Pakistani English has a distinct rhythm than RP because of this. In Pakistani English, syllables occurred at regular intervals. This is in contrast to RP, which is stress-timed with syllable length variation. The distinction between RP and Pakistani English is traditionally explained in terms of the first language. Because most South Asian

languages, including Urdu, are syllable-timed, it is assumed that Urdu speakers of English follow this pattern. Pakistani English has a syllable-timed rhythm that goes hand in hand with a lack of reduction (Mahboob & Ahmar, 2004, p. 256). However, Punjabi and Urdu have slight variances in rhythm and stress patterns, while Pashto and Sindhi have more obvious discrepancies, Pakistani speakers do not all employ the same rhythm.

Likewise, there is a frequency, pitch, and amplitude difference between Pakistani English and RP. The intonation of Pakistani English speakers differs from that of speakers of RP. This is because the intonation patterns of Pakistani languages are quite different. Likewise, Pickering and Wiltshire (2000) observed that in speakers of Indian English, including Hindi/Urdu speakers, accented syllables seemed to have a lower frequency than unaccented syllables.

Compared to A[merican] E[nglish], in which accented syllables have increasing frequency in these contexts, I[ndian] E[nglish] shows a distinct use of a decrease in frequency in accented syllables in similar contexts. This use of low frequency on accented syllables is also seen in Indian languages, suggesting a possible source (p. 177).

Pickering and Wiltshire (2000) classify South Asian English as a 'pitch-accent' language based on the use of frequency to indicate stress. They distinguish between a pitch-accent and a stress-accent language, claiming that pitch is the most important marker of accent in South Asian English. Pickering and Wiltshire (2000) also discovered that, unlike American English speakers, South Asian English speakers do not employ amplitude to indicate stress.

In conclusion, Pickering and Wiltshire (2000) state that:

There are two differences between Indian English and American English in the phonetic realization of word accent. First, American English is a stress accent language, and uses cues such as amplitude and duration as well as frequency, while Indian English uses pitch-accent, and relies primarily on the frequency to indicate an accented syllable. Second, American English indicates an accented syllable with a high frequency, while Indian English marks it with a low (p. 181).

Apart from the non-segmental traits stated above, the following can be found:

a. In RP, the stress distribution and points of junction are not always the same.

i. The stress may be distributed differently (primary stress is depicted by bold letters).

Received Pronunciation A merica Galileo	Pakistani English Am r ica Galileo
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ii. Stress may not be used to mark nouns and verbs as it is in RP. This is a characteristic of Indian English as well. (Taylor, 1969, p.31 in Kachru, 1983).

Received Pronunciation O bject (noun) O bject (verb)	Pakistani English O bject (n & v)
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iii. The primary/tertiary stress pattern for compound nouns is substituted by the secondary/primary stress pattern for free noun/noun combinations (Taylor, 1969 in Kachru, 1983, p. 31).

Besides these, the unstressed and weak syllables of English are given stronger and equal stress by non-native English speakers. Their stress patterns and points of juncture tend to be unpredictable. When the first language is an Indo-Aryan language, stress patterns deviate in the following ways:

- a) A proclivity for stressing suffixes and other non-predictable syllables rather than the penultimate syllable.
- b) A proclivity for giving weak-strong stress to nouns and verbs in a set of two-syllable words that indicate grammatical contrast through stress.
- c) There is a general lack of understanding of the primary/tertiary stress pattern for compound nouns, as opposed to the secondary/primary patterns used with free noun/noun combinations; both are used with the secondary/primary pattern.
- d) A strong tendency to give auxiliary verb forms written as contractions full value and a relatively high stress level.
- e) A tendency to break up grammatical units inside sentences arbitrarily, breaching the boundaries of 'sense groups,' and placing high stress on words those aren't ordinarily associated with 'sense stress' (Taylor, 1969).

This explanation of the phonological and phonetic aspects of English as spoken in Pakistan demonstrates how various patterns can be found in this variety. But these patterns are not the same as those of Indian English speakers. However, most phonetic features of English spoken in North India are shared by Urdu and Punjabi speakers of Pakistani English.

Method

In the present study, an effort is made to compare the Standard variety of British English with the Pakistani variety of English in order to analyse the phonetics and phonological characteristics of Pakistani English. The analysis is based on the researcher's observation and intuitive knowledge in the light of the findings of existing studies on Pakistani English, which are described in the literature review. The research starts with broad, systemic differences and then moves on to a comprehensive investigation of particular consonants, vowels, and non-segmental characteristics.

The data for this study comes from the following sources:

- a) Personal observation
- b) The written Pakistani Anglophone literature

The written Pakistani Anglophone literature includes Kamila Shamsie's *Broken Verses* (2005), Moni Mohsin's *Tender Hooks* (2011) and Nadeem Aslam's *The Blind Man's Garden* (2013). Besides that, the researcher also observed Pakistani speakers and asked them to read aloud lists of words so the researcher could abstract the characteristics of their linguistic usage.

Data Analysis, Results and Discussion

Pakistani English is best recognized by its phonological characteristics, despite the fact that phonological variation is widespread. Although RP is the norm, English pronunciation does not follow a consistent pattern across Pakistan. It is because of the influence of diverse ethnolinguistic backgrounds of Pakistani English speakers. An example of this is the variation between the placement and quality of the epenthetic vowel in English used by native Urdu, Punjabi and Hindko speakers:

Native speakers of Urdu: [ɪsku:l] 'School'
Native speakers of Hindko: [səku:l] 'School'

Another example of the variable influence of first language on Pakistani English is:

Native speakers of Urdu: [ɪsteɪʃn] 'station'
Native speakers of Hindko: [səteɪʃn] 'station'

These two examples clearly demonstrate the interference of speakers' first language on the Pakistani variety of English, which results pronunciation variations amongst speakers of Pakistani English. Therefore, rather than being absolute differences, the findings that follow are, for the most part, tendencies. These varying tendencies of Pakistani English from the RP are of two types, namely, the segmental features and the non-segmental features. Examples from the selected Pakistani Anglophone literature that are based on the researcher's observation and intuition are used to highlight these variations. They are as follows:

Segmental Features of Pakistani English

Segmental features of speech include consonant and vowel sounds or phonemes that appear in a specific temporal order. Crystal (2003) defines segmental features, as "any discrete unit that can be identified, either physically or auditory, in the stream of speech" (pp. 408–409). The following are some of the significant segmental features of Pakistani English:

A. Consonant Sounds

Consonants are classified according to three fundamental factors: place of articulation, which refers to the location in the mouth cavity where two organs make contact; manner of articulation; which refers to the way in which air stream is withheld and released; and voicing; which refers to whether or not the vocal chords vibrate. In the Pakistani variety of English, the following consonant variations predominate:

- Plosives

Only /p/, /t/, and /k/ exhibit a different realization from the RP among the plosives /p/, /t/, /k/, /b/, /d/, and /g/ in the Pakistani variety of English. These voiceless stops are not aspirated in the syllable-initial position. The word *kit*, for example, is pronounced [kɪt], without an aspiration on [k] unlike RP [k^hɪt]. This may be because aspirated and un-aspirated stops are independent phonemes in Pakistani languages. In addition, /t/ and /d/ tend to be retroflexed as in the words [ɪstrʌɽ] ‘strut’ and [dʒres] ‘dress.’

- **Fricatives**

In the Pakistani variety of English, the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/ do not exist. The voiced stop /d/ and the aspirated voiceless stop /t^h/ are realized in place of the dental fricatives /θ/ and /ð/. The voiced stop /d/ is realized for /ð/ and the aspirated voiceless stop /t^h/ is realized for /θ/, as in *thin* = [tɪn] and *then* = [den].

In addition, the phonemic distinction between the voiced labio-dental fricative /v/ and the velar semi-vowel /w/ does not exist in Pakistani English. The two sounds realized as allophones of /w/. The pronunciation of the word *power*, for example, was either [pa:wə] or [pa:və].

- **Liquids**

In Pakistani English, there are two liquids /l/ and /r/, just like in RP. However, the /l/ is generally ‘clear’ (i.e. alveolar) in Pakistani English, whereas, in RP, it has an allophonic distribution between a clear and dark /l/. But this allophonic variation does not exist in Pakistani English, as in the words: [go:l] ‘goal’ and [lɔ:t] ‘lot’. It may be because of the absence of this allophonic variation in Pakistani languages.

Pakistani English is usually referred to be a rhotic variety of English because the liquid /r/ is generally pronounced in all circumstances. While most of the other consonant sounds of Pakistani English matches RP.

B. Vowel Sounds

Vowels are classified according to three fundamental factors: the part of the tongue used for articulation (which is classified as front, central, or back); the height to which it is raised (high or close, half-close, half-open, and low or open); and the degree of lip rounding. There are two types of vowels: pure vowels and diphthongs. Pure vowels can be either long or short. All of the articulations of these vowels share the same characteristic. Vowels that transition between two qualities are known as diphthongs. In a diphthong, there are typically two audible sounds.

In comparison to RP, Pakistani English has a significantly different vowel realisation. In order to illustrate this, the researcher has developed a list of words from the Pakistani Anglophone Literature under study, with the most atypical phonetic variations based on general observations (different words have been chosen from each novel for analysis). The tabular representation below includes these words and their transcription both in the RP and Pakistani English to highlight the deviant pronunciation (for the transcription of words, an IPA chart has been used).

- **Broken Verses (2005)**

Table 1 includes words that have been extracted from Kamila Shamsie’s novel Broken Verses (2005).

Words	Received Pronunciation	Pakistani Pronunciation
Although	/ɔ:l'ðəʊ/	/ɑ:l'ðu /
All	/ɔ:l/	/ɑ:l/
Birthday	/'bɜ:θdeɪ/	/'bərθde:/
Breakfast	/'brekfəst/	/'breɪkfɑ:st/
Carpet	/'kɑ:pɪt/	/'kɑ:rpət/
College	/'kɒlɪdʒ/	/'kɑ:ləɖʒ/
Daughter	/'dɔ:tə(r)/	/'dɑ:ctər/
Determine	/dɪ'tɜ:mɪn/	/dɪ'tərmən/
Enjoy	/m'dʒɔɪ/	/m'dʒəɪ/
Energy	/'enədʒi/	/'nərdʒi:/
Film	/'fɪlm/	/'fi'ləm/
Forty	/'fɔ:ti/	/'fɑ:ti:/
Girl	/gɜ:l/	/'gərl/
Government	/'gʌvənmənt/	/'gəʊrment/
Hall	/hɔ:l/	/hɑ:l/
Horizon	/hə'raɪzn/	/'hɔ:rɪzən/
Idea	/aɪ'diə/	/'aɪdɑ:/
Immediately	/'ɪmi:diətli/	/'ɪmmi:ɖziətli:/
January	/'dʒænjuəri/	/'dʒænvri:/

Little	/'lɪtl/	/'lɪtəl/
Learning	/'lɜ:nɪŋ/	/'lɜ:rnɪŋ/
Modern	/'mɒdn/	/'mɒdrən/
Normal	/'nɔ:ml/	/'nɑ:rməl/
Orange	/'ɒrɪndʒ/	/'oʊreɪndʒ/
Police	/pə'li:s/	/pə'li:s/
Power	/'paʊə(r)/	/'pa:vər/
Quarter	/'kwɔ:tə(r)/	/k'wɑ:tər/
Recipient	/rɪ'sɪpiənt/	/rɪ'sɪ:piənt/
Record	/'rekɔ:d/	/rɪ'kɑ:(r)d/
Saw	/sɔ:/	/sɑ:/
Script	/skɪpt /	/'sɛkɪpt/
Tall	/tɔ:l/	/tɑ:l/
Translation	/træns'leɪʃn/	/trɑ:ns'leɪʃən/
Vehicle	/'vi:əkl/	/'vehɪkəl/
Want	/wɒnt/	/vɑ:nt/
Wardrobe	/'wɔ:drəʊb/	/'vɑ:drəʊb/

- *Tender Hooks (2011)*

Table 2 contains words that have been taken from Moni Mohsin's Duty Free (2011).

Words	Received Pronunciation	Pakistani Pronunciation
Accept	/ək'sept/	/ɪk'sept/
Also	/'ɔ:lsəʊ/	/'ɑ:lsəʊ/
Asthma	/'æsmə/	/'esθma:/
Allocated	/'æləkertd/	/'æləkertd/
Balloon	/bə'lu:n/	/bə'lu:n/
Conversation	/kɒnvə'seɪʃn/	/'kɒnvərseɪʃən/
Cupboard	/'kʌbəd/	/'kʌpbərd /
Date	/deɪt/	/'de:t /
Film	/fɪlm/	/fɪ'ləm/
Group	/gru:p/	/g'rʊp/
Hospital	/'hɒspɪtl/	/'hɒspɪtəl/
Modern	/'mɒdn/	/'mɒdrən/
Phone	/fəʊn/	/fu:n/
Play	/pleɪ/	/ple:/
Protagonist	/prə'tæɡənɪst/	/prə'tæɡənɪst/
Proposed	/prə'pəʊzd/	/pər'pəʊzd/
Sprite	/sprɪt/	/'səpraɪt/
Strange	/streɪndʒ/	/'sətreɪndʒ/
Spread	/spred/	/'səpred/
Strong	/strɒŋ/	/'sətrɑ:ŋ/
Station	/'steɪʃn/	/ɪs'teɪʃən/
School	/sku:l/	/ɪs'ku:l/
Table	/'teɪbl/	/'teɪbəl/
Total	/'təʊtl/	/'təʊtəl/

- *The Blind Man's Garden (2013)*

Table 3 contains words that have been taken from Nadeem Aslam's The Blind Man's Garden (2013).

Words	Received Pronunciation	Pakistani Pronunciation
Audience	/'ɔ:diəns/	/'ɑ:diəns/
Abroad	/ə'brɔ:d/	/eb'rɔ:d/
Bowl	/bəʊl/	/'bɑ:əʊl/
Butterfly	/'bʌtəflaɪ/	/'bʌtərflaɪ/
Cupboard	/'kʌbəd/	/'kʌpbərd/
Cinema	/'sɪnəmə/	/'senmə:/
Divorced	/dɪ'vɔ:sd/	/dar'vɔ:rsd/

Debt	/det/	/'debt/
Experience	/ɪk'spɪəriəns/	/eks'pɪ:riəns/
Escape	/ɪ'skeɪp/	/es'keɪp /
Fall	/fɔ:l/	/fɑ:l/
Forward	/'fɔ:wəd/	/'fɑ:rwə(r)d/
Genuine	/'dʒenjʊn/	/'dʒenʊən/
Go	/gəʊ/	/gʊ/
Here	/hɪə(r)/	/heɪr/
Horse	/hɔ:s/	/'hɑ:rs/
Information	/ɪnfə'meɪʃn/	/m'fɑ:rmɛɪʃən/
Lieutenants	/leɪ'tenənts/	/'leɪtɪnənts/
Law	/lɔ:/	/lɑ:/
Model	/'mɒdl/	/'mɑ:dəl/
Necklace	/'neɪkləs/	/'nækləs/
Occasion	/ə'keɪʒn/	/ʊ'keɪʒən/
Precise	/pri'saɪs/	/pə'r'saɪz/
Poor	/pɔ:(r)/	/'pu:ər/
Quality	/'kwɒləti/	/'kɒɑ:lɪti:/
Report	/rɪ'pɔ:t/	/rə'pɔ:rt/
Screen	/skri:n/	/'sækri:n/
Station	/'steɪʃn/	/ɪs'teɪʃən/
Target	/'tɑ:ɡɪt/	/'tɑ:rgət/
Today	/tə'deɪ/	/tu:'deɪ/
Vegetable	/'vedʒtəbl/	/'vedʒɪteɪbəl/
Vase	/vɑ:z/	/væs/
Warm	/wɔ:m/	/'vɑ:(r)m/
Zealous	/'zeləs/	/'zɪ:ləs/

The following generalizations about the vowel realisation in Pakistani English can be drawn from these word lists:

- The sound /ɔ:/ becomes /ɑ: / in words like all, although, daughter, forty, hall, and so on.
- The sound /ə/ is converted to /ɑ: / in the final position of words like cinema, data, and photography.
- In words like recipient, opponent, probably, and abroad, the sound /ə/becomes /e/.
- The sound /ɪ/ becomes /ə/ in words like credit, genuine, and college.
- In words like salute, and lieutenant, the sound /u:/ changes to /ju:/.
- The sound /e/ becomes /æ / in words like academic, balloon, and necklace.
- The sound /ə/ changes to /ʊ/ or /u: /, as in words like police, and occasion.
- In words like play, the diphthong /eɪ / is pronounced as a monophthong.
- In words like natural, the sound / æ / changes to /ei/.
- Diphthongs /əʊ/ or /oʊ/ switches to monophthongs /ʊ/ or flat 'o' sound, such as in word, go.
- In words like cinema, faculty, and quality, the sound /ə/ is not used. But it, nevertheless, inserted into words like information, congratulation, station, normal, little, hospital, total, model, pattern, and table.

However, further investigation is warranted before drawing definite conclusions about these generalised tendencies of vowel realisation in Pakistani English.

C. Gemination / Spelling Pronunciation

Since Pakistani variety of English is an institutionalised variety, it shows greater correlation between writing and speech sounds than one finds in informally acquired language. Therefore, Pakistani English tends to use spelling as a guide to pronunciation. One manifestation of this is in the gemination of consonants based on spelling. One manifestation of this is in the gemination of consonants based on spelling. All the speakers, for example geminated the [p], the [t] and the [l] in [hæppɪ] happy, [lettɹ] letter, and [kɪllɪŋ] killing. However, there are exceptions to gemination, such as the word wrapped (Ahmar & Mahboob, 2004).

In addition, the pronunciation of several words, including climb and dumb, which both have the last /b/ articulated, further demonstrates the impact of spelling. In plumber and plumbing, the sound /b/ is also articulated.

D. Simplification of Consonant Clusters

Consonant cluster simplification is another feature of Pakistani English. It occurs in a variety of ways. The most popular method is to remove some consonants from a word to make it simpler, such as *texts*, which is pronounced as /tɛks/. Besides, in non syllabic consonants, usually the vowel /ə/ or /ɪ/ is inserted before the last consonants, such as in words like, *table* as /'teɪbəl/, *hospital* as /'hɒspɪtəl/ and so on.

In addition to these, vowel /ə/ or /ɪ/ is also inserted either before or within the consonant clusters like *school* as [ɪsku:l] or [səku:l], *screen* as /'sækri:n/, *station* as /ɪs'teɪʃən/, and so on.

Non-Segmental Features of Pakistan English

Non-segmental (supra segmental) features, also called prosodic features, refer to a phonological property of more than one sound segment, which often extend over syllables, words, or phrases, such as stress, pitch, or juncture. It is in fact, the non-segmental features of the Pakistani variety of English, in which the deviation from RP is most noticeable, especially in the interaction between stress, pitch, and syllable length. Besides, unlike segmental features, these features do not seem to be influenced by the various first languages of their speakers (Kachru, 1983). Therefore, it may be argued that the Pakistani variant of English exhibits consistency of features at the non-segmental level. The following is an analysis of some significant non-segmental features of Pakistani English:

A. Syllable-Timed Rhythm

The Pakistani variety of English (it is generally assumed) has a syllable-timed rhythm, as opposed to the Standard Variety of (British) English, which has a stress-timed rhythm. As a result, whether a syllable is stressed or not, all of the syllables in Pakistani English take the same amount of time. In contrast, stressed syllables in stress-timed varieties, like RP, occur at regular intervals while the unstressed ones have been squeezed in between them. This machine-gun rhythm is one of the distinct features of Pakistani English. Since the majority of Pakistani languages are syllable-timed, the interference of the speakers' first languages is the source of the difference between Pakistani English and RP.

B. Stress Patterns

The syllable-timed rhythm of Pakistani English makes it difficult to identify patterns of stress assignment. Since each syllable receives the same amount of time, it can be challenging to distinguish between the syllables' relative prominences. Contrary to a stress-timed variety, in which stressed syllables are often realized with higher pitch, loudness, and length. Still, researcher believes that the Pakistani variety of English generally follows the following stress patterns:

- Pakistani English lays equal stress on terms that would normally have primary and secondary stress. In RP, when a word like “*anniversary*” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 17) is used, the syllable ‘*ver*’ is stressed most; however, in Pakistani English, all syllables are equally stressed, as ‘*an’ni’ver’sa’ry*’.
- In Pakistani English, there is an absence of differential patterns to mark changes in parts of speech. For example, the word “*increase*” (Aslam, 2013, p. 110) is stressed the same way in Pakistani English whether it is a verb or a noun, unlike in RP, where the stress changes as per the grammatical category, as *in’crease* (verb), and *’increase* (noun).
- In Pakistani English, auxiliary verb forms written as contractions are usually treated as whole words and accorded a relatively strong stress as opposed to the RP, which omits some sounds.
- In Pakistani English, the placement of stress frequently occurs on a different syllable than in RP, as in the word “*eco’nomiC*” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 43) in RP, which is stressed like *e’conomiC*.
- In Pakistani English, the first syllable of abbreviations is usually stressed as opposed to the last syllable in RP. Such as, “*TV*” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 53), is stressed as *’TV* instead of *T’V* in RP.
- Similar to abbreviations, compound words in Pakistani English tend to emphasize the first word rather than the second, contrary to the RP, which stresses the second word. Such as, “*’steering- wheel*” (Aslam, 2013, p. 112), “*’fifty-foot*” (Aslam, 2013, p. 115), “*’water-colour*” (Shamsie, 2005, p. 8), and “*’grape-wine*” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 54).
- Additionally, Pakistani English, as contrasted to the RP, has a tendency to arbitrarily break up grammatical units within sentences. This means that in Pakistani English, the distinction between content words—those that communicate the core meaning in a sentence—and function words—those that are crucial for the

grammaticality of a sentence—is frequently overlooked. This is due to the rhythmic differences between Pakistani English and RP.

However, despite these generalisations, Pakistani English stress patterns are often unpredictable and vary from person to person. Therefore, it may be argued that Pakistani English speakers' default stress patterns are influenced by both their ethnolinguistic and educational backgrounds and the sources from which they have learned the language.

C. Intonation

Intonation is connected to the perception of pitch, which is the frequency at which air molecules vibrate while someone speaks. Variations in the voice's pitch are the main factor in intonation. It frequently works in tandem with rhythm and stress in languages like English to produce meaning. In RP, pitch serves a number of functions. A variation in pitch, for example, used to express contrastive meaning. However, in Pakistani English pitch contrasts are used less frequently. Pakistani English users do often lengthen the final syllable as a form of emphasis. Besides that, the Pakistani variety of English; regardless of the weak forms of vowels or contractions in auxiliary verb forms, takes more time to utter similar English language components than RP because of its syllable-timed rhythmic patterns.

Although a thorough analysis of the intonation of Pakistani English has not yet been undertaken, a generalised view indicates that Pakistani English tends to use three intonation patterns: falling intonation, rising intonation, and fall-rise intonation. The falling intonation is usually used in declarations, directives, and sometimes in exclamations. While a rising intonation is used for tag questions, yes-no questions, and to some of the 'wh' questions. Likewise, dependent clauses reflect rising intonation. Fall-rise intonation, on the other hand, denotes incompleteness or reservation. However, in Pakistani English, rising and falling intonation patterns are used more frequently than fall-rise intonation.

The researcher has intuitively analyzed the intonation patterns of some of the following sentences from the Pakistani Anglophone literature under study. Such as, these sentences have falling intonation patterns, for example:

- “‘Nicknames and friendship rarely go ↘ together,’ I said” (Shamsie, 2005, p. 13).
- “I occasionally write ↘ haiku” (Shamsie, 2005, p. 14).
- “Pussy!” Mummy hissed. “People are ↘ looking” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 10).
- “Promise ↘ me” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 10)!
- “‘Thank you, uncle. And I am ↘ sorry’” (Aslam, 2013, p. 285).
-

These sentences have rising intonation patterns, as:

- “Which of your Lord’s blessings would you ↗ deny” (Shamsie, 2005, p. 10)?
- “Are you here for ↗ *Boond*” (Shamsie, 2005, p. 11)?
- “Head cracked, fainted, not to ↗ worry. Not to ↗ worry” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 13)?
- “That you were from same sort of ↗ baggrounds” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 20)?
- “‘What are you doing ↗ here’” (Aslam, 2013, p. 16)?
- “‘You are going to ↗ Afghanistan’” (Aslam, 2013, p. 17)?

Besides that, in Pakistani culture, intonation patterns also reflect social status and politeness strategies. As a result, when speaking to subordinates, Pakistani speakers use falling intonation, and when speaking to strangers, they use rising intonation patterns. For example, when asked to strangers, the following Wh-questions have a rising intonation.

- “I picked it up with gratitude and an unfamiliar voice on the other end said, ‘↗Aasmaani Inqalab’ (Shamsie, 2005, p. 9)?
- “‘Who are ↗ you?’ I asked (Mohsin, 2011, p. 121).
- “‘Who are ↗ you?’ the man says” (Aslam, 2013, p. 300).
- “‘What is your ↗ name’ (Aslam, 2013, p. 300)?

Conversely, when the same questions are directed toward one's social inferiors or subordinates, the intonation is usually falling.

However, it is quite challenging to generalise the intonation patterns or pitch change, as it is stated under stress patterns, Pakistani English, in contrast to the RP, tends to arbitrarily break up grammatical units within sentences. Therefore, it needs further investigation to draw some conclusions.

D. Some other Aspects of Connected Speech

In the Pakistani variety of English, emphasis, exaggeration, and surprise are expressed phonologically by stretching both consonants and vowels (which are occasionally echoed orthographically, too) as well as by repeating particular words (Upper case letters are sometimes used in writing to reflect this feature of Pakistani English) as in the examples below:

- “Jonkers is **so** happy, so happy that don’t even ask” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 175).
[extra long / o: / in so]
- “Stupid” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 17).
[extra long /p/ in stupid, which is also used orthographically with an extra p]
- “The man gives what must be his happiest smile” (Aslam, 2013, p. 216).
[extra long /p/ in happiest]

Repetitions of words to express emphasis, exaggeration or surprise as:

- “No, no. That’s what you *do*” (Shamsie, 2005, p. 126).
- “No, no, that’s not true” (Shamsie, 2005, p. 242).
- “‘Welcome, welcome!’ said Zeenat” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 28).
- “Honestly the sich is so bad, so bad that don’t even ask” (Mohsin, 2011, p. 57).
- “No, no, no, no,’ Mikal says under his breath” (Aslam, 2013, p. 276).

Conclusion

In this study, the researcher has made an effort to provide a concise review of the phonetics and phonological features of Pakistani English at segmental and non-segmental levels. The description of these features, however, is based on the researcher’s observation, intuitive understanding and conceptual framework laid down in literature review. Although some features are distinct enough to be considered diagnostic of Pakistani English, it is challenging to determine their level of stability because even among the educated speakers of Pakistani English, there are individual variations in pronunciation. These individual variations are the result of a variety of factors, such as the speakers’ ethnolinguistic backgrounds, educational levels, institutions they have attended, and the contexts in which they use the language.

Therefore, as with English speech in any institutionalised variety, the complexity of Pakistani English pronunciation makes it challenging for one account to cover all of the nuances. However based on the findings, it can safely be said that the phonetics and phonological features of Pakistani English differ considerably from the

Recommendations

This preliminary study of the phonetics and phonological features of Pakistani English is intended to serve as the foundation for further research and improvements in the domains of segmental and non-segmental features of Pakistani English. Such as, a detailed phonetic evaluation of Pakistani English vowels is still desired. Likewise, intonation patterns or pitch change needs further investigation to draw some conclusions.

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